

Kinetics of Silver-Catalysed Oxidation of Dimethyl-Formamide by Potassium Peroxydisulphate

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The kinetics of Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of d.m.f. by peroxydisulphate ion in aqueous medium has been investigated. The reaction is found to be first order w.r.t. $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, zero order w.r.t. d.m.f. but the specific rate is a function of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and d.m.f. concentration. It decreases with an increase in $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ concentration but increases with an increase in d.m.f. concentration. The specific rate is linearly related to (Ag^+) by an expression $k = 1.7 \times 10^{-3} + 1.6 (\text{Ag}^+)$. K^+ exerts a strong specific inhibitory effect on the rate. The temperature coefficient, energy of activation, frequency factor and entropy of activation have been determined. The mole ratio is found to be 1 : 1 and the final products are $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NH}$, CO_2 and H_2O . On the basis of these kinetic results, a possible reaction mechanism has been proposed.

Peroxydisulphate ion has been lately used to bring about the oxidation of several classes of organic compounds and the kinetics of some of these processes have been studied by different workers. These studies upto 1962 have been reviewed by House¹. Recently the interest in such kinetic studies by peroxydisulphate ion has greatly increased. Firstly peroxydisulphate ion is a milder oxidising agent than other conventional oxidants and hence the investigation of the intermediate stages in the oxidation of organic substrates may be feasible and secondly very often the kinetic behaviour does not follow a simple order. Mention may be made of the studies on the oxidation of oxalic acid by Allen and coworkers², by Bhakuni and Srivastava³, by Gupta and Ghosh⁴, of alcohols by Levitt and Malinowski⁵, by Edwards and coworkers⁶, by Wiberg⁷ and by Khulbe and Srivastava⁸. However, a review of the literature shows that no systematic study on the kinetics of oxidation of amides by peroxydisulphate ion has been made. The only previous work reported is the study of oxidation of acetamide and formamide by Mushran and coworkers⁹⁻¹⁰. Hence a systematic study of the oxidation of different amides by peroxydisulphate ion is being undertaken. The present paper deals with the kinetic results obtained for silver catalysed oxidation of dimethyl-formamide by peroxydisulphate ion.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium peroxydisulphate Analar B.D.H. was used after recrystallisation and drying at room temperature under vacuum. Its standard solution was made daily by direct weighing of the recrystallised salt, and dissolving in redistilled water. Its strength was verified by the same iodometric method as used in the present kinetic study. Dimethyl-formamide E. Merck G.R. was used after redistillation and its standard solution was prepared by dissolving its calculated volume in redistilled water. Other chemicals used were also of Analar quality.

The reaction was carried out by running in calculated volume of potassium persulphate solution in the reaction vessel containing the other reactants, immersed in a thermostatic water bath maintained at the temperature of the experiment with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. At suitable intervals of time the reaction mixture was estimated for the remaining peroxydisulphate by the iodometric method of Szabo, Csanyi and Galiba¹¹ as modified by Khulbe and Srivastava¹².

Blank estimation of peroxydisulphate in presence of dimethylformamide was first carried out to test the accuracy of this method in the present case.

RESULTS OF MEASUREMENT

Preliminary experiments showed that the reaction has a measurable speed at 35° or so and therefore the present kinetic study was carried out at 35° , unless otherwise specified. The self decomposition of peroxydisulphate ion was also studied under similar conditions in each case from which the specific rate for the dimethyl formamide reaction has been evaluated by subtraction since both the reactions are found to be first order in behaviour. The typical kinetic runs at different concentrations of peroxydisulphate ion are represented graphically in Fig. 1; the curves for self decomposition being represented in the upper part of the figure by the corresponding A curves.

FIG 1 EFFECT OF PEROXYDISULPHATE CONCENTRATION
 $[Aq NO_3] = 0.001M$, $[HCON (CH_3)_2] = 0.001M$ TEMP. $35^\circ C$
 $[K_2 S_2 O_8] = I. 5 \times 10^{-3} M$, II. $7.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ III. $1 \times 10^{-2} M$.
 IV. $1.5 \times 10^{-2} M$, V. $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$

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It is seen that the reaction follows a first order behaviour at all these concentrations of peroxydisulphate ion.

Kinetic runs were then made at different initial concentrations of d.m.f. The specific rate values evaluated graphically in both the kinetic sets are tabulated below:

TABLE I

$K_2S_2O_8$ conc. M	$AgNO_3 = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$		Temp. 35°		
	d.m.f. conc. M	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k_2 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k \times 10^3 = (k_1 - k_2)$ $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
0.005	0.01	6.78	1.70	5.08	
0.0075	0.01	6.06	1.44	4.62	
0.01	0.01	5.12	1.34	3.78	
0.015	0.01	3.84	1.21	2.63	
0.02	0.01	3.39	1.15	2.24	
0.01	0.005	3.84	1.34	2.50	
0.01	0.015	6.40	1.34	5.06	
0.01	0.02	7.43	1.34	6.09	
0.01	0.025	9.60	1.34	8.26	

An examination of the above data shows that the first order specific rate is a function of peroxydisulphate ion as well as d.m.f. concentration, it decreases with an increase in peroxydisulphate ion concentration, but increases in a linear manner with an increase in d.m.f. concentration (c.f. the effect of peroxydisulphate ion and alcohol concentration on the oxidation of alcohols^{5,6}).

The effect of peroxydisulphate ion concentration on the specific rate may be due partly to the increase in ionic strength and partly to the specific inhibitory effect of potassium ions. A reference to the subsequent work on the effect of ionic strength, will however, show that this decrease is much more than to be accounted for due to the above two causes.

Effect of silver nitrate concentration: The kinetic results obtained at different concentrations of silver nitrate as catalyst are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

AgNO ₃ conc.	$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.01 M, HCON(CH_3)_2 = 0.01 M$ Temp. 35°					
	0.00025M	0.0005M	0.001M	0.0015M	0.002M	0.0025M
$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	2.40	3.45	5.12	6.17	6.90	8.82
$k_2 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.36	0.77	1.34	1.97	2.47	3.20
$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1} = k_1 - k_2$	2.04	2.68	3.78	4.20	4.43	5.62

An examination of the above data shows that the specific rate increases with an increase in AgNO₃ concentrations, the specific rate being related to AgNO₃ concentration by the relationship

$$k = 1.7 \times 10^{-3} + 1.6 C_{Ag^+}$$

It may be mentioned that similar behaviour has been reported in other Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of different substrates by peroxydisulphate ion.

Effect of temperature : The reaction was studied at four different temperatures for evaluating the energy parameters, the results for which are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III

$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.01M$, $\text{HCON}(\text{CH}_3)_2 = 0.01M$; $\text{AgNO}_3 = 0.001M$

Temp. in $^\circ\text{A}$	$k \times 10^3$ min $^{-1}$	Temp. coeff.	Energy of activation (ΔE) in Kcals. per mole	Frequency factor litre mole $^{-1}$ sec $^{-1}$. $\text{A} \times 10^{-7}$	Entropy of activation ΔS E.U.
303	2.38			11.80	-23.63
308	3.78	2.53	17.47	11.71	-23.67
313	6.03	2.40	17.11	11.92	-23.67
318	9.09			11.60	-23.75
	Mean	2.465	17.29	11.757	-23.68

It is found that a plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ is linear showing that the reaction obeys Arrhenius equation, the value of energy of activation evaluated from this graph being 17.16 Kcals mole $^{-1}$. It may be mentioned that energy of activation for other Ag^+ catalysed oxidations of organic substrates by peroxydisulphate ion studied in this laboratory are also of similar order of magnitude and a negative entropy of activation has been reported in these reactions.

Specific effect of ions : The specific effect of K^+ , Na^+ , H^+ and Zn^{++} ions have been investigated. The results of these studies are tabulated below :

TABLE IV

$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 0.01M$, $\text{HCON}(\text{CH}_3)_2 = 0.01M$, $\text{AgNO}_3 = 0.001M$ Temp. 35°

Cations added	Conc. (M)	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min $^{-1}$	$k_2 \times 10^3$ min $^{-1}$	$k \times 10^3 = k_1 - k_2$ min $^{-1}$
—	—	5.12	1.34	3.78
K_2SO_4	0.04	2.88	0.88	2.00
Na_2SO_4	0.04	4.11	0.96	3.15
H_2SO_4	0.04	4.42	1.09	3.33
Zn SO_4	0.04	4.60	1.15	3.45

An examination of the above data shows that of all ions investigated, K^+ ion has strong specific inhibitory effect. In view of the specific inhibitory effect exhibited, the effect of ionic strength could not be investigated.

Mole ratio and products of reaction : The mole ratio between potassium peroxydisulphate and dimethyl-formamide, after taking into account the self decomposition of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ in presence of the catalyst, comes out to be one mole of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ to one mole of d.m.f. The

reaction mixture on testing for the possible reaction products gave the test for formic acid in the earlier stages but after 12 hours only dimethyl amine was found present in the reaction mixture, it giving no test for formic acid. This suggests that formic acid first formed, as a result of hydrolysis, is oxidised to carbon dioxide and water, while dimethyl amine, the other product of hydrolysis remains unaffected.

DISCUSSION

The first order behaviour of the reaction w.r.t. to $S_2O_8^{-2}$, zero order with respect to d.m.f., linear relationship between specific rate and Ag^+ , strong specific inhibitory effect of K^+ , decrease of specific rate with an increase in potassium peroxydisulphate and increase of specific rate with an increase in d.m.f. concentration all go to show that this reaction is very much similar to the Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of alcohols by peroxydisulphate ion studied by Khulbe and Srivastava⁸ and others. These similarities in kinetic behaviour together with the fact that the mole ratio is one suggest to us that the reaction follows the following mechanism :

It is worthwhile to point out that the first two steps have been proposed by Srivastava and coworkers in other silver catalysed oxidation reactions of different substrates by peroxydisulphate ion¹²⁻¹⁵ also. Since the rate of disappearance of peroxydisulphate ion is governed by process (1), the rate of the reaction can be rather simplified to

$$\frac{-d[S_2O_8^{-2}]}{dt} = k[S_2O_8^{-2}][Ag^+]$$

in conformity with the experimental results. However, the above equation is rather an oversimplified representation of this reaction because it does not account for the variation of specific rate with change in either potassium peroxydisulphate or d.m.f. concentration, although it is in agreement with the mole ratio observed, and the mechanism proposed. It is, however, clear that the oxidation of d.m.f. is, in fact, the oxidation of formic acid

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formed as a result of hydrolysis. If so, the oxidation of different amides by peroxydisulphate ion should show similar kinetic behaviour and rates of similar order of magnitude. Further work with other amides to substantiate the above mechanism is in progress.

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Received December 28, 1969
Revised MSS received March 23, 1971